

Radiation Shielding Analysis for Spent Fuel Salt in Maritime Environments

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I. INTRODUCTION

As the nuclear industry explores innovative solutions for spent fuel management, ensuring effective radiation shielding remains a paramount concern, particularly during the transport and storage phases. This is even more critical in maritime environments, where unique challenges arise due to the inherent constraints on weight and spatial dimensions imposed by the vessel's architecture. Traditional land-based shielding strategies often prove inadequate or infeasible when directly transposed to maritime settings.

Maritime transport of nuclear materials, such as spent fuel salt from Molten Salt Reactors (MSR), presents an opportunity to leverage the fluid physical form of molten salts for adaptive shielding configurations. The adaptability of molten salt allows for the creation of shielding geometries that can seamlessly integrate into the standardised cargo containers commonly used in maritime logistics. This integration not only addresses the physical constraints of shipping environments but also aligns with established cargo handling practices, potentially simplifying logistical operations involved in nuclear fuel transport.

Adams *et al.* [1] review existing designs and concepts for MSR spent nuclear fuel (SNF) and concludes that interim storage and transportation of SNF still poses a gap in research. The knowledge is limited to experience acquired from the Aircraft Reactor Experiment (ARE) 1954 [2] and the Molten Salt Reactor Experiment (MSRE) 1965-1969 [3]. Unfortunately, the handling concepts of the MSRE SNF are barely documented in existing literature; Ougouag *et al.* [4] touch upon shielding and handling issues and proposes to package the SNF in NUHOMS-type containers [5] during transportation. However, after the reactor shutdown in 1969, the fuel salt was drained into two tanks. Several years later, uranium was removed from the fuel salt, but the residual fuel salt, contaminated with fission products, remains until today in the drain tanks [1], [6]. Oak Ridge National Laboratory never conducted a detailed evaluation nor addressed whether the proposed approach would meet packaging specifications, as

illustrated by the preference of the U.S. Department Of Energy (DOE) to entomb the MSRE on-site [7], [8].

The authors seek to address the outlined challenges by proposing an initial framework for the handling of MSR SNF during transportation and interim storage, marking a preliminary step toward a comprehensive solution. While this study will not cover all aspects of MSR SNF management such as chemical separation and stabilisation technologies [9], it aims to initiate a discourse on practical and feasible approaches to the identified gap in the MSR fuel cycle. This paper delves into the radiation shielding analysis for SNF of containers specifically tailored for maritime conditions. Utilising advanced Monte Carlo-based simulation techniques, the study investigates the material choice and geometric configuration that meet the stringent safety standards required for minimising radiation exposure during transport as well as interim storage.

II. MARITIME ENVIRONMENTS

The following sections give a brief overview of materials and conventions already prevalent in ship construction that can be readily adapted for radiation shielding purposes. It also touches upon the rigorous radiation safety standards and requirements that must be met in maritime environments.

A. Technology Maturity

In developing radiation shielding solutions for spent nuclear fuel in maritime environments, a significant advantage lies in leveraging the existing infrastructure of cargo containers. This approach simplifies transportation logistics by utilising widely available and standardised container sizes, thus avoiding the need for new handling technologies or methods. However, these containers present challenges in terms of their limited width and height. Surprisingly, the constraints on dimensions are not as critical as those imposed by weight limits, which are predominantly influenced by the shielding materials required to meet safety standards.

Traditionally, materials such as water and concrete are used for gamma shielding in land-based reactors due to their cost-effectiveness and availability. Yet, their relatively low photon

attenuation coefficients necessitate impractically thick layers to achieve adequate shielding [10], rendering them unsuitable for the confined spaces of standard cargo containers. Steel and lead offer higher attenuation coefficients and could minimise the required shielding material volume [10]; notably, the high efficiency of lead could be particularly beneficial. However, its use in maritime applications is limited by the absence of established supply chains and the lack of familiarity with lead handling in shipyard settings. This necessitates the development of new logistical and processing capabilities to integrate such materials into existing maritime operations. Consequently, with AH32 steel [11] commonly used and readily available in shipyards, steel emerges as the only feasible shielding material, already compatible with existing maritime manufacturing processes.

B. Radiation Safety Compliance

The requirements to ensure safe handling, transportation, and storage of radioactive materials are generally governed by international and national regulations and standards, such as those from the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) [12] and the U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission (NRC) [9]. Key aspects of radiation safety compliance for SNF transportation containers involve limits on surface dose rates, required margin to criticality for fissile materials, decay heat removal capabilities, containment of volatile fission products, and structural integrity of the container to protect during accident scenarios. The requirements for containers can vary significantly depending on several factors, including the medium of transportation, the type of material contained, and specific safety category targeted by the operator. A comprehensive overview of these safety requirements is found in [9], [12].

III. GEOMETRY & SPENT NUCLEAR FUEL

A representative geometry of a fuel container was modelled and is shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2 it encompasses a cylinder of 88.4 litres SNF and 10 litres of air headspace in a stainless steel SS316 tank with a thickness of 3 cm. SS316 can withstand higher temperatures than AH32; in practice one would most likely also need an inner coating to prevent corrosion; this is not considered in this study. The cylinder is placed on a 67 cm high block of AH32. This block serves together with the surrounding 5 cm thick AH32 inner containment wall as a barrier if the tank fails to retain the SNF. The inner containment wall is separated from the shielding material by a 10 cm wide air space which could possibly be used for decay heat removal. The radiation shield is in each direction 50 cm thick and consists of steel type AH32. The described geometry is placed into a conventional 10ft cargo container (304.8 cm x 251.2 cm x 239.4 cm) with walls of 0.4 cm thickness and a bottom plate of 2 cm; the space in between is filled with air at atmospheric pressure.

FIGURE 1: SIDE VIEW OF THE SNF TRANSPORTATION CONTAINER; LEFT GEOMETRY, RIGHT IMPORTANCE MAP. PINK REPRESENTS SNF, GREY IS STEEL AND WHITE IS AIR.

For the creation of a representative SNF, key parameters of the conceptual MSR from Zhu *et al.* [13] were adopted. The 150 MWth reactor is fueled with $\text{LiF-BeF}_2\text{-ThF}_4\text{-UF}_4$ with an initial enrichment of 19.75 %. The fuel salt volume is $\sim 10 \text{ m}^3$ in the primary circuit and the operational lifetime is set to 10 years. The fuel was burned in several burnup steps in a Serpent2 [14] model with an infinite lattice similar to the one given in [13]. The acquired isotopic composition subsequently underwent several decay steps in the geometry detailed above; neutron radiation is ignored in this study to focus on the attenuation of gamma radiation.

FIGURE 2: TOP VIEW OF THE SNF TRANSPORTATION CONTAINER. TOP HALF SHOWS GEOMETRY; LOWER HALF VISUALISES THE IMPORTANCE MAP FOUND IN THE ITERATIVE WWG.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Global Variance Reduction

To model the photon transport throughout the container, we employ a Monte Carlo-based simulation method since traditional point kernel methods applied to large sources often fail to yield results with sufficiently low uncertainty in a multilayer system like the one under study. Given the considerable distances high energy photons cover and the strong attenuation desired in such environments, brute force Monte Carlo simulation techniques become computationally expensive. To mitigate this, our approach incorporates a global variance reduction, particularly weight-window generation (WWG) applied across the spatial domain [15]. It was found that the third iteration between Monte Carlo simulation and the response matrix solver of a geometry-based adaptive scheme and an implicit source sampling is able to populate the entire geometry as seen in Figure 1 and Figure 2; therein, we applied a subdivision by 2 of the initial 125-cell coarse mesh in each direction with a density split criterion of 3 g/cm³. The weight-window mesh was subsequently imported into a model with an increased number of particles to determine the volume averaged photon flux throughout the geometry and the surface averaged flux at the outer surface of the cargo container. This final simulation was repeated for various decay steps to study the behaviour of dose rate over time. With the help of conversion coefficients for radiation exposure in the antero-posterior direction [16] the equivalent dose rate in Sievert per hour was determined.

B. Construction of an Efficiency Curve

The global variance reduction method represents a significant improvement compared to brute force Monte Carlo-based method simulations in terms of uncertainty and simulation time. Furthermore, for strong changes in emission

FIGURE 3: EMISSION SPECTRUM, EFFICIENCY CURVE, THEIR PRODUCT AND THE CONVERSION FACTOR CURVE ICRP FROM [16] AS FUNCTION OF PHOTON ENERGY.

spectrum, a single weight-window mesh failed to simulate the transport correctly. Including also the energy domain into the WWG would increase requirements on memory and WWG becomes more complex.

However, when there is a change solely in the emission spectrum, it is unnecessary to repeat the entire photon transport simulation for each decay step. One can bin the SNF emission spectrum into energy groups and simulate for each of these energy groups a mono-energetic source with a source rate of 1 particle per second with a low uncertainty utilising the WWG method. In this way one retrieves an attenuation efficiency M_i [-] for the energy group i ; one can finally infer the total dose rate D [$\mu\text{Sv/h}$] at the detector from a given binned photon flux Φ_i [$1/\text{cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$] and the conversion factor C_{ICRP} [$\mu\text{Sv/h cm}^2\text{s}$] [16] as the sum over i energy groups of $M_i \cdot \Phi_i \cdot C_{ICRP}$; the different constituents of the method are visualised in Figure 3. With this approach, one can effortlessly explore a vast parameter space as it does not necessitate additional computationally intensive photon transport simulation, only the analysis of binned emission spectra.

V. RESULTS

Our study of the shielding efficiency of the above detailed geometry revealed the following findings. The container passes the imposed criticality requirements since a deeply subcritical multiplication factor of $k_{eff} = 0.13$ was observed when all air spaces were flooded with water, even for fresh fuel. A recriticality accident can thus be avoided despite the presence of fissile materials in the salt. By applying the WWG and efficiency curve assisted method, we were able to assess the dose rates at the external surface of the container with sufficiently low uncertainty. Table 1 shows a comparison between the two approaches of this study and benchmarks them to an analog Monte Carlo simulation with a significantly higher uncertainty and number of simulated particles, thus simulation time. The analog value serves merely as an illustration to showcase that several orders of magnitude more particles still result in such a high uncertainty. Overall, we see good agreement; the methods detailed above are consistent within their uncertainties.

TABLE 1: COMPARISON OF EQUIVALENT DOSE RATE AT THE EXTERNAL SURFACE OF THE CONTAINER FOR A 10 YEAR BURNUP, 1 MINUTE DECAY TIME IN $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ FOR THREE PROPOSED SIMULATION TECHNIQUES.

Analog Monte Carlo ($1 \cdot 10^{11}$ particle)	Self-adaptive WWG ($2 \cdot 10^8$ particle)	WWG & efficiency curve ($3 \cdot 10^{10}$)
33.96 +/- 44%	42.11 +/- 3.6%	44.19 +/- 1.1%

Once the efficiency curve is determined for the given geometry, further analysis only requires studying the source term from depletion calculations. This enables studies of a wide

FIGURE 4: SURFACE AVERAGED EQUIVALENT DOSE RATE AT THE EXTERNAL SURFACE OF THE CONTAINER AS A FUNCTION OF BURNUP AND SUBSEQUENT DECAY TIME.

parameter space such as the impact of burnup and decay time on dose rate, shown in Figure 4. Therein, we observe a relatively high dose rate at short decay times irrespective of the burnup. However, for longer decay times (> 400 days), the burnup significantly influences the dose rate. This high initial dose rate is primarily governed by radionuclides with short half-lives and high-energy gamma emissions, which rapidly achieve a production-decay equilibrium. Conversely, for decay times exceeding 400 days, the dose rate becomes increasingly influenced by the burnup. In this regime, the dose rate is governed by longer-lived isotopes, which accumulate over extended periods of time before establishing a production-decay equilibrium. Therefore, fuel samples subjected to longer operational durations exhibit an elevated dose rate at high decay times due to the prolonged accumulation of these isotopes.

Finally, we assess the effectiveness of the shielding configuration, shown in Figure 5. Our findings indicate that the

FIGURE 5: VOLUME-AVERAGED EQUIVALENT DOSE RATE AS A FUNCTION OF DISTANCE FROM THE CENTRE OF THE GEOMETRY FOR A 10 YEAR BURNUP AND VARIOUS DECAY TIMES. BACKGROUND COLOUR SCHEME OF FIGURE 1 IS APPLIED.

reduction in equivalent dose rate is almost consistent across all decay steps; one can observe a slightly weaker attenuation for the low decay times. This is due to the gamma emission spectrum becoming softer over time and thus increasing the attenuation efficiency. Furthermore, the magnitude of the absolute value is significantly influenced by the specific decay step. Notably, only decay times exceeding 10 days are feasible due to residual decay heat. Additionally, it was observed that the dose rates drop below the background radiation level of $\sim 1 \mu\text{Sv/h}$ [17] before reaching the end of the shielding material for these extended decay times. Considering that the permissible exposure limits for the transportation of SNF are considerably higher [12] and given the inherent advantage of a MSR lies in removing fission products during operational phases [3], [18] - thereby reducing the source term strength of MSR SNF - the necessary shielding thickness is substantially less than modelled in this study.

VI. CONCLUSION

The presented study initiates a first effort to address the identified research gaps of MSR SNF handling, transport, and interim storage. A first geometry for a container was proposed which is compatible with already existing standards in the maritime environments simplifying the introduction of such a system. Furthermore, two different approaches for evaluation of such deep penetration problems were applied and agree well with one another as shown in Table 1. WWG combined with an attenuation efficiency curve allowed for a rapid assessment of the radiotoxicity of the fuel for varying burnup and decay times. Finally, the shielding efficiency of the proposed container design was investigated. Findings indicate, an optimization study is required to find a balance between SNF volume and shielding thickness to determine the optimal geometry while adhering to lifting capacity constraints of standard cargo cranes. Future work will include a more realistic container model, studies of decay heat removal and the SNF inherent neutron source.

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] G. Adams, P. LaPlante, and Y.-M. Pan, "Assessment of the Current State of Knowledge on Storage and Transportation of Molten Salt Reactor Waste," U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission, RES-DE-REB-2023-5, 2023.
- [2] W. B. Cottrell, H. E. Hungerford, J. K. Leslie, and J. L. Meem, "Operation of the Aircraft Reactor Experiment," Oak Ridge National Laboratory, ORNL-1845, 1955. [Online]. Available: <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/4237975>
- [3] P. N. Haubenreich and J. R. Engel, "Experience with the Molten-Salt Reactor Experiment," *Nucl. Appl. Technol.*, vol. 8, 1970, doi: 10.13182/NT8-2-118.

- [4] A. M. Ougouag, P. A. Ostby, and R. L. Nebeker, "Evaluation of potential for MSRE spent fuel and flush salt storage and treatment at the INEL," Lockheed Idaho Technologies Co, Idaho Falls, INEL--96/0329, 1996.
- [5] L. A. Strobe, M. A. McKinnon, D. J. Dyksterhouse, and J. C. McLean, "NUHOMS Modular Spent-Fuel Storage System: Performance Testing," Electric Power Research Institution, EPRI-NP-6941, 1990. [Online]. Available: <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/6469544>
- [6] F. J. Peretz, "Identification and evaluation of alternatives for the disposition of fluoride fuel and flush salts from the molten salt reactor experiment at Oak Ridge National Laboratory," Oak Ridge National Laboratory, ORNL/ER-380, 1996. [Online]. Available: <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/441122>
- [7] L. M. Krall, A. M. Macfarlane, and R. C. Ewing, "Nuclear waste from small modular reactors," *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, vol. 119, no. 23, 2022, doi: 10.1073/pnas.2111833119.
- [8] "Feasibility of In Situ Decommissioning of Fuel and Flush Salt at the Molten Salt Reactor Experiment," Department of Energy - United States of America, DOE/OR/01-2793 & D1, 2018.
- [9] "Standard Review Plan for Transportation Packages for Spent Nuclear Fuel," U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission, Final Report NUREG-1617.
- [10] A. Ali and M. A. Mubarak, "Gamma Ray Shielding," Pakistan Institute of Nuclear Science & Technology, Islamabad, PINSTECH/HP-10, 1971.
- [11] American Society for Testing and Materials, "Standard Specifications for Structural Steel for Ships," ASTM International, A 131/A 131M-14, 2014.
- [12] *Regulations for the Safe Transport of Radioactive Material*, Text SSR-6, Vienna., 2018. doi: 10.61092/iaea.ur52-my90.
- [13] G. Zhu *et al.*, "Neutronic effect of graphite dimensional change in a small modular molten salt reactor," *Int. J. Energy Res.*, vol. 45, no. 8, pp. 11976–11991, 2021, doi: 10.1002/er.5964.
- [14] J. Leppänen, M. Pusa, T. Viitanen, V. Valtavirta, and T. Kaltiaisenaho, "The Serpent Monte Carlo code: Status, development and applications in 2013," *Ann. Nucl. Energy*, vol. 82, pp. 142–150, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.anucene.2014.08.024.
- [15] J. Leppänen and M. Jokipii, "Global variance reduction scheme with self-adaptive weight-window mesh in the Serpent 2 Monte Carlo Code," *Int. Conf. Math. Comput. Methods Appl. Nucl. Sci. Eng.*, pp. 85–95, 2019.
- [16] "Conversion Coefficients for Radiological Protection Quantities for External Radiation Exposures," International Commission on Radiological Protection, ICRP Publication 116, 2010.
- [17] United Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiation, Ed., *Sources and effects of ionizing radiation I: Sources*. in Sources and effects of ionizing radiation, no. 2008. New York: United Nations, 2010.
- [18] P. Jr. Vicente Valdez, B. Betzler, W. Wieselquist, and M. Fratoni, "Modeling Molten Salt Reactor Fission Product Removal with SCALE," ORNL/TM-2019/1418, Feb. 2020. doi: 10.2172/1608211.